

Australopithecus sediba:
an internal dental perspective

Thomas W. DAVIES

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U.W. 88-8 (MH1) – right mandible fragment with M₁-M₃.

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Australopithecus sediba: an internal dental perspective

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ABSTRACT

The tooth crown morphology of *Australopithecus sediba* Berger *et al.*, 2010 has so far only been described at the outer enamel surface, which limits the accessible morphological information, particularly in the case of worn teeth (such as those of adult individual MH2). Microtomographic imaging allows us to study internal dental structures such as the enamel-dentine junction (EDJ), which preserves the morphology of important dental features even in cases of moderate tooth wear, as well as allowing us to assess crown tissue proportions. Here I present the first assessment of the internal dental structure of *A. sediba*, providing descriptions of the mandibular postcanine EDJ morphology, scoring the expression of discrete traits, measuring 2D molar enamel thickness, and comparing to *Australopithecus* R.A.Dart, 1925, *Paranthropus* Broom, 1938 and *Homo* Linnaeus, 1758. The EDJ clarifies the expression of molar accessory cusps in the species; the absence of lingual accessory cusps (C7) in the M₁ and M₂ is consistent with *Australopithecus*, and distinct from early *Homo*. Well-developed protostylid crests extend mesially beyond the protoconid, which is most similar to *A. africanus*. Examination of the molar EDJ also reveals an unusual feature; the apparent rotation of the EDJ crown in occlusal view relative to the outer enamel surface, clearest in the M₂ of MH1, which warrants further investigation. Molar enamel thickness (MH1; M₂, M₃) is found to be similar to other *Australopithecus* in absolute terms, but as the molars of MH1 are small, the enamel is thick in relative terms, within the range of *Paranthropus*. Relatively thick enamel could aid in hard-object feeding, as has been previously suggested for the species.

KEY WORDS

Australopithecus sediba,
Malapa,
enamel-dentine junction,
dental morphology,
enamel thickness.

RÉSUMÉ

Australopithecus sediba : une perspective dentaire interne.

La morphologie de la couronne dentaire d'*Australopithecus sediba* Berger *et al.*, 2010 n'a, jusqu'à présent, été décrite qu'au niveau de la surface extérieure de l'émail, limitant ainsi les informations morphologiques accessibles aux chercheurs, en particulier dans le cas de dents usées (comme celles de l'individu adulte MH2). L'imagerie microtomographique nous permet d'étudier les structures dentaires internes, telles que la jonction émail-dentine (EDJ) qui préserve la morphologie de caractéristiques dentaires importantes, même dans le cas d'usures dentaires modérées, et nous permet également d'évaluer les proportions des tissus de la couronne. Je présente ici la première étude des structures dentaires internes d'*A. sediba*. Celle-ci se base sur la description de caractères discrets de la morphologie de la jonction émail-dentine des molaires et prémolaires de la mandibule, et sur la mesure de l'épaisseur de l'émail des molaires. Ces données sont ensuite comparées aux taxons *Australopithecus* R.A.Dart, 1925, *Paranthropus* Broom, 1938 et *Homo* Linnaeus, 1758. L'observation de l'EDJ met en avant l'expression particulière des cuspidés accessoires sur les molaires d'*A. sediba*; l'absence de cuspidés accessoires linguales (C7) au niveau des M₁ et M₂ est cohérente avec *Australopithecus*, et distincte des premiers *Homo*. Les crêtes du protostylide sont bien développées, et s'étendent mésialement au-delà du protoconide, ce qui est similaire à *A. africanus*. L'examen de l'EDJ des molaires révèle également une caractéristique inhabituelle : la rotation apparente de l'EDJ en vue occlusale par rapport à la surface externe de l'émail, plus nette chez la M₂ de MH1, ce qui nécessitera une étude plus approfondie. Enfin, l'épaisseur de l'émail des molaires (MH1 ; M₂, M₃) est similaire à celle d'*Australopithecus* en termes absolus, mais comme les molaires de MH1 sont petites, l'émail est relativement plus épais, dans la variation de *Paranthropus*. L'émail relativement épais pourrait aider à se nourrir d'objets durs, comme cela a déjà été suggéré pour cette espèce.

MOTS CLÉS
Australopithecus sediba,
 Malapa,
 jonction émail-dentine,
 morphologie dentaire,
 épaisseur de l'émail.

INTRODUCTION

Australopithecus sediba Berger *et al.*, 2010 is known from the site of Malapa in South Africa; the species hypodigm includes two well-preserved partial skeletons of a juvenile (MH1, the type specimen) and an adult (MH2; (Berger *et al.* 2010)). The remains are dated to 1.98 Ma (Pickering *et al.* 2011), making *A. sediba* the latest surviving currently known species of *Australopithecus* R.A.Dart, 1925. The relationship between *A. sediba* and other hominin species remains a topic of debate. Morphological similarities across the skeleton with *A. africanus* Dart, 1925 suggest a close relationship between the two species (Berger *et al.* 2010; Kimbel & Rak 2017). However, several features of the cranium in particular have been interpreted as *Homo*-like, such as the slight postorbital constriction, lack of flaring zygomatics and widely spaced temporal lines. These features have been used to argue the species could be the ancestor of *Homo* Linnaeus, 1758 (Berger *et al.* 2010), supported by the results of a phylogenetic analysis of craniodental characters (Dembo *et al.* 2015). However, cranial features are only preserved in the type specimen, MH1, a juvenile individual, and Kimbel & Rak 2017 have argued that the features of the MH1 cranium that are interpreted as *Homo*-like may instead be due to its ontogenetic status. This debate has continued in recent years, with a phylogenetic analysis by Mongle *et al.* (2023) finding that even when ontogenetically influenced characters were excluded, an *A. sediba* – *Homo* clade could not be rejected. Alternatively, Du & Alemseged (2019) use temporal evidence to argue against *A. sediba* as

the ancestor of *Homo*. The Malapa fossils are 800 000 years younger than the earliest known *Homo*; even assuming budding cladogenesis that would allow for an ancestral taxon to persist after the emergence of its decendent, they argue that this scenario is highly unlikely.

Dental remains are an important source of evidence in addressing taxonomic and phylogenetic questions in paleo-anthropology – many dental features are known to be under strong genetic control, and, unlike bones, teeth are not remodelled throughout an individual's lifetime. The dental morphology of *Australopithecus sediba* has been characterized through descriptions and comparisons with other hominins (Berger *et al.* 2010; de Ruiter *et al.* 2013, 2018), analysis of discrete dental traits (Irish *et al.* 2013) and dental crown measurements (Irish *et al.* 2016). These studies underline the distinctive morphology of the teeth of *A. sediba*; the teeth are small, but have several similarities to other australopiths, and *Australopithecus africanus* in particular. Irish *et al.* (2013) outline several dental features shared between *A. sediba* and *A. africanus*, including the expression of M₁ protostylid and M₁ Carabelli's cusp. Similarly, the expression of premolar buccal grooves and thick marginal ridges are suggested to be australopith-like (de Ruiter *et al.* 2018). Alternatively, some aspects of the dentition have been interpreted as being similar to early *Homo*; in particular, the teeth are smaller than is typical of *Australopithecus* (Berger *et al.* 2010; de Ruiter *et al.* 2013), and the relative tooth size patterns across the dental arcade are suggested to most closely resemble *Homo* species (Irish *et al.* 2016).

FIG. 1. — MH1 mandibular molars and premolars shown at the enamel surface and enamel-dentine junction. Accessory cusps are marked with **red arrows**. *P3 and P4 images are reversed so that all teeth appear as right sided. Scale bar: 10 mm.

TABLE 1. — Summary of *Australopithecus sediba* Berger *et al.*, 2010 teeth analysed in this study and resolution of the corresponding micro-CT scan.

Individual	Accession	Tooth	Resolution
MH1	U.W. 88-246	Left P ₃	28 µm
	U.W. 88-244	Left P ₄	28 µm
	U.W. 88-8	Right M ₁ -M ₃	31 µm
MH2	U.W. 88-129	Right P ₃	32 µm
	U.W. 88-128	Right P ₄	32 µm
	U.W. 88-54	Right M ₁ -M ₂	50 µm
	U.W. 88-55	Left M ₃	31 µm

However, a limiting factor in studies of external tooth morphology is dental wear. This is a particular issue in the adult individual MH2; majority of teeth are heavily worn, which obscures the majority of crown features. The teeth of MH1 are less worn as this individual is a juvenile, however wear on the M₁ is still sufficient to obscure key features such as accessory cusps. Imaging techniques such as micro-CT scanning can allow us to study internal dental structures, including the enamel-dentine junction (EDJ) which underlies the enamel cap, and is preserved in cases of moderate tooth wear. This is useful as the majority of dental crown features originate at the EDJ, and its morphology can provide an insight into the developmental basis of crown features, which is important in establishing trait homology (Bailey *et al.* 2011; Anemone *et al.* 2012; Martínez de Pinillos *et al.* 2014; Ortiz *et al.* 2017; Davies *et al.* 2021; Chapple & Skinner 2023).

Additionally, micro-CT scanning allows for the non-destructive assessment of crown tissue proportions such as enamel thickness, which can be informative for taxonomic purposes, as well as in understanding tooth development and interpreting dietary adaptations of fossil taxa (Martin 1985; Beynon & Wood 1986; Grine & Martin 1988; Schwartz 2000; Kono 2004; Smith *et al.* 2005; Lucas *et al.* 2008; Olejniczak *et al.* 2008; Skinner *et al.* 2015).

Here I provide the first assessment of the inner structural morphology of the *A. sediba* dentition. I analyse the morphology of the EDJ, the expression of discrete dental traits, and measure molar enamel thickness to test whether the mandibular postcanine dentition of *Australopithecus sediba* shows closer affinities to *Australopithecus* or early *Homo*.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

SAMPLE

The sample consists of mandibular postcanine teeth (P₃-M₃) from two *Australopithecus sediba* individuals, MH1 (Fig. 1) and MH2 (Fig. 2), previously described at the enamel surface by de Ruiter *et al.* (2018). Where both antimeres are available, the better-preserved tooth, or the tooth with better scan quality, was used. Specimens were scanned with a Nikon Metrology XTH 225/320 LC CT-system at the Evolutionary Studies Institute at the University of the Witwatersrand (MH2; see Daegling *et al.* 2016 for details), a Nikon XT H 225 at Danfix, Technical University of Denmark (MH1 premolars), or the

ID19 beamline at the at the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility in Grenoble (MH1 molars; see Irish *et al.* 2016 for details). The resulting study sample and scan resolutions are summarized in Table 1.

SEGMENTATION

TIFF stacks were filtered using a mean of least variance filter with a kernel size of one, using MIA open source software (Wollny *et al.* 2013). Filtered image stacks were used to segment enamel from dentine using a seed growing watershed algorithm employed via a custom plugin in Avizo 6.3 (Visualization Sciences Group), before being checked manually, with checks against the unfiltered image stack where necessary. Once enamel and dentine were segmented, a triangle-based surface model of the EDJ was produced using the unconstrained smoothing parameter in Avizo and then saved in polygon file format (.ply).

ENAMEL THICKNESS

Enamel thickness was measured in 2D following the protocol of Skinner *et al.* (2015) for the M₂ and M₃ of MH1 (the M₁ of MH1 and all MH2 molars are too worn to measure enamel thickness. The comparative sample for enamel thickness was taken from (Skinner *et al.* 2015); consisting of M₂s and M₃s of *Australopithecus* (*Australopithecus afarensis*; A.L.128-23, A.L.145-35, A.L.241-14, A.L.333w-1a, A.L.333w-32, A.L.400-1a, and *Australopithecus africanus*; MLD2, StW3, StW14, StW61, StW109, StW133, StW213, StW280, StW308, StW327, StW384, StW404, StW412B, StW498c, StW520, StW529, StW537, StW555, StW560, StW586), *Paranthropus* Broom, 1938 (*Paranthropus robustus* (Broom, 1938); DNH60C, SK1, SK6, SK23, SK25, SKW5, SK75, SK81, SK843.846a, SK851, SK1587a, SKX4446, SKX5014, SKX10643, TM1600, and *Paranthropus boisei* Leakey, 1959; L427-7, L628-3, Omo47-1973-1500, KNM-ER 3230, KNM-ER 15930) and *Homo* (*Homo* sp.; KNM-ER 1506A, KNM-ER 1802, and *Homo erectus* (Dubois, 1893); KNM-BK 67, KNM-ER 992, KNM-ER 1507).

MORPHOLOGICAL DESCRIPTION

The EDJ morphology of each tooth is described, and discrete dental traits are scored using previously described scoring systems in order to standardise comparisons with other fossil hominins. Mandibular premolar traits (transverse crest, marginal ridges and buccal grooves) are scored following Davies *et al.* (2019). For mandibular molars, accessory cusps are scored following the protocol of Davies *et al.* (2021) and trigonid crests were scored following (Bailey *et al.* 2011). No scoring system is currently available for the protostylid at the EDJ, but this feature will be described and compared with other published material. Comparative data for discrete traits are taken from the published literature where available, or where unavailable, are scored here using surface models of the EDJ. The comparative sample consists of 100 molars and 71 premolars of *Australopithecus* (*A. afarensis* and *A. africanus*), *Paranthropus* (*Paranthropus aethiopicus*, *P. robustus* and *P. boisei*) and *Homo* (*Homo* sp., *H. habilis*, and *H. erectus*).

FIG. 2. — MH2 mandibular molars and premolars shown at the enamel surface and enamel-dentine junction. Accessory cusps are marked with **red arrows**. *M3 images are reversed so that all teeth appear as right sided. Scale bar: 10 mm.

TABLE 2. — Molar enamel thickness means and standard deviations for each taxon and tooth position. *, Skinner *et al.* (2015) incorrectly list two M_2 s (DNH60C and SK6) as M_1 s, which has been corrected here. Additionally, KNM-ER 15930 M_1 is incorrectly listed as an M_2 ; the corrected measurements are added here.

Taxon	Tooth	AET (mm)		RET	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD
<i>Australopithecus</i>	M_2	1.62	0.21	23.52	3.20
	M_3	1.74	0.17	23.98	3.05
<i>Paranthropus</i> *	M_2	2.13	0.27	30.22	4.62
	M_3	2.12	0.31	28.89	4.06
<i>Homo</i>	M_2	1.49	0.17	24.78	2.42
	M_3	1.37	0.16	23.03	4.04
<i>A. sediba</i> (MH1)	M_2	1.71	–	26.56	–
	M_3	1.80	–	26.78	–

All descriptions refer to the EDJ unless otherwise specified, but comparisons with the outer enamel surface morphology are given where there are important differences.

ABBREVIATIONS

AET average enamel thickness;
 EDJ enamel-dentine junction;
 RET relative enamel thickness.

RESULTS

ENAMEL THICKNESS

Enamel thickness data for MH1 and the comparative sample are summarised in Table 2 (raw measurement data for MH1 are given in Appendix 1). There is some overlap between taxa in both AET and RET, although there is more overlap in RET (Fig. 3). In AET, the M_2 of MH1 is closest to the *Australopithecus* mean, but is also within the upper limit of the *Homo* range (slightly lower AET than KNM-ER 1802) and within the lower limit of the *Paranthropus* range. The M_3 is closest to the *Australopithecus* mean, within the lower end of the *Paranthropus* range, but well outside of the *Homo* range (although my sample size is small, and the M_3 of KNM-ER 1802, the *Homo* specimen with the highest M_2 AET value, could not be measured due to damage). In RET, both M_2 and M_3 are in the upper range of *Australopithecus*, and within the interquartile range of *Paranthropus*, suggesting that both teeth have relatively thick enamel for their size.

EDJ MORPHOLOGY

Enamel dentine junction morphology is described below for each tooth position in MH1 and MH2.

MH1 PREMOLARS

(U.W. 88-246 LP₃; U.W. 88-244 LP₄; Fig. 1)

Both MH1 mandibular premolars show minimal occlusal wear with no dentine exposure.

The P_3 is asymmetrical in occlusal view, with a broad protruding buccal face and a large talonid such that the posterior fovea is narrower than the anterior fovea. The metaconid is well-developed and positioned mesially relative to the protoconid. There are two small accessory cusps mesial of the

protoconid, one midway along the mesial protoconid ridge, and one at the meeting point of the mesial protoconid ridge and the mesial marginal ridge. A small accessory cusp is also visible on the mesial marginal ridge. The distal marginal ridge has two accessory cusps, one distolingually and one distally positioned, and a final accessory cusp is present at the meeting point of the distal marginal ridge and the distal protoconid ridge. There is a low transverse crest that connects to both main cusps (Type 1; Davies *et al.* 2019). Two accessory crests run into the distal fovea, one originating at the protoconid, and another originating midway along the distal ridge of the protoconid. The second is associated with a broad raised portion of the distal protoconid ridge. The mesial and distal marginal ridges are continuous (Type C; Davies *et al.* 2019), but are less sharp on the mesial and distal portions of the metaconid. On the buccal face, there are buccal grooves that extend most of the height of the crown. The distal buccal groove is more strongly expressed than the mesial (Mesial Type 1, Distal Type 2; Davies *et al.* 2019). There is also an additional crest on the buccal face that runs at an oblique angle from beneath the protoconid distal horn, terminating close to the distal buccal groove.

The P_4 is rectangular in occlusal view; the buccal face is broad and protruding as in the P_3 , and the talonid is well-developed, but the anterior fovea is as wide as the posterior fovea. The metaconid is similar in height to the protoconid, and positioned slightly mesial of the protoconid. The metaconid is also slightly internally placed. There is a small accessory cusp at the meeting point of the mesial protoconid ridge and the mesial marginal ridge. There are two very small accessory cusps on the mesial marginal ridge which are barely visible, but correspond to two small accessory cusps at the enamel surface. As in the P_3 there are two accessory cusp on the distal marginal ridge, one mesiolingually and one distally positioned, and one accessory cusp at the meeting point of the distal marginal ridge and the distal protoconid ridge. The transverse crest runs continuously between the two cusps (Type 1; Davies *et al.* 2019). An accessory crest runs from the metaconid into the central fovea. There is also a low accessory crest that runs from the middle of the distal protoconid crest into the central fovea; this crest is similarly positioned to one seen in the P_3 , but it is less well-developed in the P_4 . The mesial and distal marginal ridges are continuous (Type C; Davies *et al.* 2019). On the buccal face, marked mesial and distal buccal grooves are present (Mesial Type 2, Distal Type 2; Davies *et al.* 2019), but the mesial buccal groove is shortened in length and does not extend as far in the occlusal direction as in the P_3 . Also similar to the P_3 , the buccal face has an additional crest that runs from beneath the protoconid at an oblique angle towards the bottom of the distal buccal groove.

MH2 PREMOLARS

(U.W. 88-129 RP₃; U.W. 88-128 RP₄; Fig. 2)

Moderate occlusal wear in the MH2 premolars has removed a number of crown features, particularly on the buccal side of the crown. However, a number of aspects of EDJ morphology remain.

FIG. 3. — Enamel thickness in mandibular second and third molars, measured using 2D average enamel thickness (AET) and relative enamel thickness (RET). *Australopithecus sediba* Berger *et al.*, 2010 teeth are shown using horizontal lines, and compared to *Australopithecus* R.A.Dart, 1925 (*A. africanus* Dart, 1925, *A. afarensis* Johanson, White & Coppens, 1978), *Homo* Linnaeus, 1758 (*Homo* sp., *H. erectus* (Dubois, 1893)) and *Paranthropus* Broom, 1938 (*P. boisei* Leakey, 1959, *P. robustus* (Broom, 1938)). Comparative data from Skinner *et al.* (2015).

The P₃ is asymmetrical in occlusal view, with a broad protruding buccal face and a moderately large talonid. There is a tall transverse crest that likely connected to both cusps, although wear has removed both cusp tips (probable Type 1; Davies *et al.* 2019). The distal marginal ridge is continuous and has a small accessory cusp, while the mesial marginal ridge is also continuous, although it is lowered immediately mesial of the metaconid (Type C; Davies *et al.* 2019). The buccal face shows moderately expressed mesial and distal buccal grooves that extend most of the height of the crown (Mesial Type 1, Distal Type 1; Davies *et al.* 2019).

The P₄ is asymmetrical in occlusal view due to a mesiobuccally protruding buccal face that is narrow compared to the other *A. sediba* premolars, including the P₄ of MH1. The talonid is large. The metaconid is worn but was mesially placed. There is one accessory cusp present on the distal marginal ridge, distolingually positioned, which is slightly worn. The dentine is worn across the entire buccal aspect of the marginal ridges. The exposed dentine is wider at the distobuccal portion of the crown, which suggests a raised portion of the marginal ridge, likely representing an additional accessory cusp at the meeting point of the distal protoconid crest and distal marginal ridge, as is seen in MH1. Both mesial and distal marginal ridges are continuous (Type C; Davies *et al.* 2019) and well-developed. There is no evidence of a transverse crest in the occlusal basin and only small incipient crests are present on the preserved portion of the metaconid (probable Type 0; Davies *et al.* 2019). The narrow buccal face has deeply incised but short mesial and distal buccal grooves (Mesial Type 2, Distal Type 2; Davies *et al.* 2019) that are angled obliquely towards one another, and nearly meet due to the narrowness of the buccal face of the tooth.

MH1 MOLARS (U.W. 88-8 RM₁-M₃; Fig. 1)

There is light occlusal wear on the M₁ that has removed only the tips of the protoconid and hypoconid, but there is no dentine exposure on the M₂ or M₃.

In occlusal view, the M₁ has an ovorectangular outline, slightly reduced at the distobuccal corner and strongly pinched at the centre of the lingual and buccal faces. All five primary cusps are present and well-developed. There is a small distal accessory cusp/C6 (Hypoconulid type; Davies *et al.* 2021). The distal accessory cusp is slightly internally placed on a crest that connects the distal marginal ridge to the entoconid. There are two small mesial accessory cusps. The protoconid and metaconid are joined by their essential ridges to form a low but continuous middle trigonid crest (Grade 2; Bailey *et al.* 2011). There are also several smaller discontinuous crests that may be considered as part of the expression of trigonid crests (see Martínez de Pinillos *et al.* 2014); a small crest running from the middle trigonid crest into the mesial fovea, two small crests/wrinkles running distally from the middle trigonid crest (close to the metaconid), and a small crest on the distal ridge of the protoconid. There is also a larger crest mesial of the hypoconid running into the occlusal basin, and the aforementioned crest running from the entoconid to the distal marginal ridge. On the buccal face of the EDJ, there is a well-developed protostylid crest that extends mesially beyond the protoconid dentine horn tip, and continues distally to the hypoconid, extending a small distance in the occlusal direction. There is also a short but well-developed distal protostylid crest on the hypoconulid.

The M₂ is slightly wider on the mesial side of the crown in occlusal view, tapering distally, and as in the M₁, is pinched at

FIG. 4. — Mandibular M₂ of MH1 displaying the apparent rotation of the EDJ crown in occlusal view. Figure shows the OES (A), EDJ (B), and both surfaces overlaid with transparent enamel (C).

the centre of the lingual and buccal faces. An unusual aspect of the morphology of this tooth is that in occlusal view the mesiodistal axis of the EDJ crown appears rotated relative to that of the enamel surface (Fig. 4). This is the result of the position of several crown features, and is particularly noticeable at the mesial marginal ridge, which is angled differently at the enamel and dentine surfaces, and the exaggerated protrusion of the entoconid at the enamel surface. As in the M₁, all five primary cusps are present, but there are no accessory cusps. The marginal ridges are well-developed, and the distal ridge of the metaconid is high and shows some shouldering (Skinner *et al.* 2008; Martin *et al.* 2017; Ortiz *et al.* 2017; Davies *et al.* 2021). The essential ridges of the protoconid and metaconid form a low middle trigonid crest. The crest appears to be interrupted in the middle of the occlusal basin, although an enamel defect immediately above the EDJ precludes a more definite assessment (Grade 1 or 2; Bailey *et al.* 2011). There are additional crests on the distal ridges of the protoconid and metaconid, as well as mesial and distal of the entoconid, and mesial of the hypoconid. On the buccal face, a well-developed mesial crest extends beyond the protoconid dentine horn, but does not extend as far distally as the equivalent crest in the M₁, and is angled apically at its distal end (rather than occlusally, as in the M₁). There is also a small interruption in the mesial crest, beneath the protoconid dentine horn. The distal crest is also present beneath the hypoconulid, and is better developed than in the M₁.

The M₃ also tapers distally in occlusal view, more so than in the M₂. The rotation of the EDJ crown relative to the enamel surface is also visible in this tooth, although it is less notable than on the M₂ and clearer in the distolingual portion of the crown. All five main cusps are present, and there are no accessory cusps. The distal ridge of the metaconid shows shouldering as in the M₂. Both the protoconid and metaconid have ridges that deflect mesially and do not meet such that there is no continuous trigonid crest (Grade 1; Bailey *et al.* 2011); the metaconid ridge meets the mesial marginal ridge (although it is significantly lowered immediately distal of the mesial marginal ridge), while the protoconid ridge terminates

close to the mesial marginal ridge. There are also two small crests on the distal ridge of the metaconid and one on the distal ridge of the protoconid that run towards the occlusal basin. Additionally, there are crests either side of the entoconid, and a bifurcated crest on the hypoconid. Protostylid crests are similar to the M₂ – there is a well-developed, uninterrupted mesial crest that extends beyond the protoconid on the mesial end, and extends apically at the distal end. The distal crest is more strongly expressed than in M₁ or M₂; it is well-developed and extends further across the buccal face in a mesiobuccal direction.

MH2 MOLARS

(U.W. 88-54 RM₁-M₂; U.W. 88-55 LM₃; Fig. 2)

The molars of MH2 are more heavily worn than MH1 – the M₁ has large dentine exposures and the mesiolingual corner of the crown is missing, the M₂ is less worn but still has dentine exposures on all cusps, while the M₃ only has dentine exposures on the mesial cusps.

In the M₁, all five principal cusps were present. There is no evidence of accessory cusps, but it is important to note that there is significant wear, and part of the metaconid is missing. Therefore, accessory cusps close to the main cusps (particularly the metaconid) could be missed, as could very small accessory cusps as this tooth was scanned at a lower resolution (50 µm). The preserved portion of the occlusal basin between the protoconid and metaconid shows evidence of a low trigonid crest, but the cusps are too worn to identify whether it ran continuously between the two cusps. Another crest is present that appears to have connected the entoconid and hypoconulid. Protostylid crests are well-developed; the mesial crest extended mesially to, or likely beyond, the protoconid dentine horn. The distal crest is also deeply incised, and both crests extend occlusally some way below the hypoconulid.

As in MH1, the M₂ EDJ of MH2 appears rotated relative to the outer enamel surface, although it is more difficult to assess in this tooth due to the high level of wear. The crown has an ovorectangular outline, slightly reduced at the distobuccal

TABLE 3. — Enamel-dentine junction expression of discrete dental traits in *A. sediba*. *Uncertainty in trait expression due to wear, breakage or enamel defect – see main text for details

Tooth type	EDJ feature	Tooth	MH1	MH2
Molars	Lingual accessory cusp	M ₁	None	None*
		M ₂	None	None*
		M ₃	None	Metaconid type
	Distal accessory cusp	M ₁	Hypoconulid type	None*
		M ₂	None	None*
		M ₃	None	Interconulid type
	Trigonid crest	M ₁	Grade 2	–
		M ₂	Grade 1 or 2*	Grade 0
		M ₃	Grade 1	Grade 0
Premolars	Premolar buccal grooves (Mesial, Distal)	P ₃	Type 1, Type 2	Type 1, Type 1
		P ₄	Type 2, Type 2	Type 2, Type 2
	Premolar transverse crest	P ₃	Type 1	Type 1*
		P ₄	Type 1	Type 0*
	Premolar marginal ridges	P ₃	Continuous	Continuous
		P ₄	Continuous	Continuous

corner as in the M₂ of MH1. All five cusps were present and there is no evidence of accessory cusps (as in the M₁, small accessory cusps could have been missed due to lower scan resolution). There is no continuous trigonid crest, only weakly expressed ridges (Grade 0; Bailey *et al.* 2011); the essential ridge of the protoconid runs into the occlusal basin, and another small crest is present distal of the protoconid. The mesial protostylid crest is well-developed and extends mesially beyond the protoconid dentine horn, but does not extend distally to the hypoconid, instead deflecting apically. There is a short distal protostylid crest on the hypoconulid.

In occlusal view, the M₃ is also reduced at the distobuccal corner, more so than the M₂. All five principal cusps are present, as well as a distal accessory cusp/C6 (Interconulid type; Davies *et al.* 2021) and a lingual accessory cusp/C7 (Metaconid type; Davies *et al.* 2021). There is no continuous trigonid crest, only weakly expressed ridges on the protoconid and metaconid that extend centrally into the occlusal basin, and an additional crest that runs distally from the metaconid (Grade 0; Bailey *et al.* 2011). There are also crests running from all other cusps into the occlusal basin; two from the hypoconid, one from the hypoconulid and two small crests from the entoconid. As in the M₂, there is a well-developed mesial protostylid crest that extends mesially beyond the protoconid dentine horn. There is also a distal protostylid crest, but the crest extends further apically than in the M₁ and M₂.

DISCRETE TRAITS

The EDJ expression of discrete dental traits in MH1 and MH2 is summarised in Table 3. Data for the comparative sample is summarised for molar traits in Table 4, and premolar traits in Table 5 (see Appendices 2; 3 for full data).

Molar accessory cusp patterns are clearest in the M₁; *Paranthropus* M₁s most often have distal accessory cusps (8/10) and no lingual accessory cusps (10/10), while *Homo* has the opposite pattern (8/9 have a lingual accessory cusp, and none have distal accessory cusps). In *Australopithecus*, accessory cusps are rarer, but distal accessory cusps are more common (4/13 have distal accessory cusps, while none have

lingual accessory cusps). MH1 therefore fits the australopith pattern (only a distal accessory cusp), while MH2 has no visible M₁ accessory cusps, similar to *Australopithecus*. Patterns in the M₂ and M₃ are more variable in *Australopithecus* and *Homo*, but MH1 lacking distal accessory cusps distinguishes it from *Paranthropus*.

Trigonid crests are variable, but they are common in *Australopithecus* M₁s (7/10), as seen in MH1 (MH2 also has a trigonid crest, but it is too worn to assess if it runs continuously between cusps). However, a continuous trigonid crest is also seen in 4/10 *Paranthropus* M₁s and the M₁ of OH 13 (*H. habilis*). For M₂s and M₃s, *Paranthropus* shows a clear pattern of absence of continuous trigonid crests, but absence of such crests are also common in *Australopithecus* (only 8/30 M₂s and M₃s show continuous trigonid crests), and *Homo* (4/13 M₂s and M₃s show continuous trigonid crests). Therefore the absence of these crests in MH2 and the M₃ of MH1 is not informative (the M₂ of MH1 shows a low trigonid crest that is also likely discontinuous – see above).

Premolar transverse crests that runs continuously between the two cusps (Type 1) are the most common form in all taxa, as seen in both *A. sediba* P₃s and the P₄ of MH1. While the P₄ of MH2 is heavily worn, it is clear that there is no transverse crest in the occlusal basin (Type 0). This is relatively common in *Paranthropus* (5/12), but is also seen in one *A. africanus* specimen: StW 213.

Both *A. sediba* individuals have premolars with continuous marginal ridges, however this is the most common form in all taxa, so is not taxonomically informative. Buccal grooves are variable across taxa: the P₃ of MH1 has a moderate mesial buccal groove and marked distal buccal groove, which is not seen in the *Homo* sample (*n* = 6), and is more common in *Australopithecus* (and to a lesser extent, *Paranthropus*). Both MH1 and MH2 P₄s have marked mesial and distal buccal grooves. Marked mesial buccal grooves are absent in *Paranthropus* P₄s (*n* = 11), but are found in 4/13 *Australopithecus* and 1/4 *Homo* P₄s. Marked distal buccal grooves are most common in *Homo* (2/4), but are also seen in *Paranthropus* (3/11) and *Australopithecus* (3/13).

TABLE 4. — Summary of presence/absence scores for molar discrete traits in the comparative sample. Full data can be found in Appendix 2. Presence absence scores are given for each trait; for lingual and distal accessory cusps, present means at least one accessory cusp was scored, while for trigonid crests Grades 2 and 3 are considered present, referring to the presence of a continuous crest (Bailey *et al.* 2011). Abbreviations: **DAC**, distal accessory cusp; **LAC**, lingual accessory cusp; **TC**, trigonid crest.

		LAC		DAC		TC	
		%	n	%	n	%	n
<i>Australopithecus</i>	M ₁	0.0%	13	30.8%	13	70.0%	10
	M ₂	27.8%	18	44.4%	18	27.8%	18
	M ₃	41.7%	12	25.0%	12	25.0%	12
<i>Homo</i>	M ₁	88.9%	9	0.0%	10	33.3%	3
	M ₂	27.3%	11	54.5%	11	50.0%	6
	M ₃	70.0%	10	60.0%	10	14.3%	7
<i>Paranthropus</i>	M ₁	0.0%	10	80.0%	10	40.0%	10
	M ₂	0.0%	9	100.0%	9	0.0%	9
	M ₃	28.6%	7	100.0%	7	0.0%	7

DISCUSSION

The postcanine teeth of MH1 are relatively small, at the lower end of the *A. africanus* range and comparable to some early *Homo* (Berger *et al.* 2010; Irish *et al.* 2016). In absolute terms, enamel thickness (AET) in the M₂ and M₃ of MH1 is most similar to *Australopithecus*; however, when standardised for tooth size (RET), enamel thickness is higher, within the interquartile range of *Paranthropus*. The M₂ and M₃ therefore have relatively thick enamel for teeth of their size. Enamel thickness is known to be variable even among closely related species, and changes in enamel thickness can occur relatively quickly (Hlusko *et al.* 2004; Ungar & Hlusko 2016), which may make it particularly prone to homoplasy, creating difficulties for studies of taxonomy (Skinner *et al.* 2015). However, these changes can be informative for reconstructing hominin diets. Thick enamel can be interpreted as an adaptation to hard object feeding that protects the tooth against fracture or chipping (Walker 1981; Grine & Martin 1988; Lucas *et al.* 2008), or alternatively as an adaptation to extend the life of the tooth in the case of gradual microscopic wear (Molnar & Gantt 1977; Rabenold & Pearson 2011; Ungar & Sponheimer 2011). In the case of *A. sediba*, dental micro-wear, isotopic and phytolith data indicate the consumption of hard foods, and diet dominated by C3 plants including tree bark (Henry *et al.* 2012). Such a diet including hard objects would be aided by relatively thick enamel that reduces the susceptibility of the tooth to fracture. Although this thicker enamel would be offset somewhat by the small tooth size (see Constantino *et al.* 2011; Schwartz *et al.* 2020) and apparent mechanical limits on high bite forces in the MH1 cranium (Ledogar *et al.* 2016), it is still likely that *A. sediba* was capable of hard-object feeding as a component of its diet (Daegling *et al.* 2016; Grine & Daegling 2017, also see van Casteren *et al.* 2019). The morphology of the earliest members of the genus *Homo* is in a number of regards very similar to that of *Australopithecus* (Wood 1992; Spoor *et al.* 2015; Kimbel & Villmoare 2016; Davies *et al.* 2024), which can create challenges in distinguishing between the two groups. In terms of

dental traits, however, molar accessory cusps are important (Wood & Abbott 1983; Wood 1991; Irish *et al.* 2013; Ortiz *et al.* 2017; Davies *et al.* 2021), and the EDJ helps to clarify the expression of these accessory cusps in *A. sediba*. A previous study of the enamel surface inferred that, despite dental wear, an M₁ lingual accessory cusp (C7) was likely present in MH1 and MH2, and this could represent a synapomorphy between South African australopiths and *Homo* (Irish *et al.* 2013). However, at the EDJ, no lingual accessory cusps are present in any of the molars of MH1, and only in the M₃ of MH2 (although there is some uncertainty due to the missing portion of the M₁ crown – see results section). EDJ observations suggest that accessory cusp expression is complex; for example OES accessory cusps can be represented at the EDJ by multiple differing cusp morphologies (see Ortiz *et al.* 2017; Davies *et al.* 2021). Therefore, some caution should be taken in the use of these features for taxonomy. However, despite these complications, the M₁s of early *Homo* show a high frequency of lingual accessory cusp presence (8/9), and a low frequency of distal accessory cusp presence (0/10) at the EDJ (Table 4). Previous work has also shown that this combination of features is common in *H. habilis* in particular, and is rare in *Australopithecus* (Davies *et al.* 2021). MH1 shows the opposite condition, and therefore differs from early *Homo*, with accessory cusp expression more similar to *Australopithecus*. Specimens from South Africa suggested to belong to early *Homo* show a variety of accessory cusp expressions; the molars of SK 15 do not have EDJ lingual accessory cusps, but a recent study of the EDJ shape has questioned the *Homo* status of this and other South African specimens (Zanolli *et al.* 2022), and as such they are not included in the comparative sample used here.

Protostylid features are present and well-expressed in M₁–M₃ in both MH1 and MH2, with well-developed crests that extend mesially beyond the protoconid dentine horn on the mesiobuccal side of the crown. This is similar to the morphology seen in a number of *A. africanus* specimens (Skinner *et al.* 2009), consistent with results of the enamel surface (Irish *et al.* 2013). *Paranthropus robustus* molars tend to have protostylid crests that are more centrally located on the buccal face (Skinner *et al.* 2009), while *Homo erectus* and Middle Pleistocene *Homo* specimens tend to have more weakly expressed and shorter protostylid crests, when present (Zanolli & Mazurier 2013; Zanolli 2015; Skinner *et al.* 2016; Xing *et al.* 2018). No study has so far systematically examined protostylid crests in early *Homo*, but *H. habilis* specimens show variable expression of protostylid features. The molars of the type specimen OH7 do not have protostylids, and although there are protostylid features on some other *H. habilis* molars (e.g. OH16), few express the well-developed and elongated crests seen in *A. sediba* (see images in Davies *et al.* (2024)). The development of a scoring system for the protostylid at the EDJ would allow us to better understand inter-taxon variation in this feature.

At the EDJ, continuous trigonid crests are common in Neanderthals (Bailey *et al.* 2011), hominins from Sima de los Huesos (Martínez de Pinillos *et al.* 2014), Arago and Montmaurin-La Niche (Martínez de Pinillos *et al.* 2020), but are less frequent in *H. sapiens* (Bailey *et al.* 2011) and

TABLE 5. — Summary of premolar discrete traits in the comparative sample (full data can be found in Appendix 3).

Transverse crest				
Taxon	Tooth	Type 0	Type 1	Other
<i>Australopithecus</i>	P ₃ (n = 11)	0.0%	100.0%	0.0%
	P ₄ (n = 13)	7.7%	84.6%	7.7%
<i>Homo</i>	P ₃ (n = 6)	0.0%	83.3%	16.7%
	P ₄ (n = 5)	0.0%	80.0%	20.0%
<i>Paranthropus</i>	P ₃ (n = 11)	18.2%	81.8%	0.0%
	P ₄ (n = 12)	41.7%	50.0%	8.3%

Marginal ridges			
Taxon	Tooth	Continuous	Discontinuous
<i>Australopithecus</i>	P ₃ (n = 15)	66.7%	33.3%
	P ₄ (n = 12)	100.0%	0.0%
<i>Homo</i>	P ₃ (n = 6)	66.7%	33.3%
	P ₄ (n = 5)	100.0%	0.0%
<i>Paranthropus</i>	P ₃ (n = 12)	100.0%	0.0%
	P ₄ (n = 11)	100.0%	0.0%

Buccal grooves							
Taxon	Tooth	Mesial buccal groove			Distal buccal groove		
		0	1	2	0	1	2
<i>Australopithecus</i>	P ₃ (n = 16)	0.0%	18.8%	81.3%	0.0%	62.5%	37.5%
	P ₄ (n = 13)	53.8%	15.4%	30.8%	23.1%	53.8%	23.1%
<i>Homo</i>	P ₃ (n = 6)	16.7%	0.0%	83.3%	50.0%	50.0%	0.0%
	P ₄ (n = 4)	25.0%	50.0%	25.0%	25.0%	25.0%	50.0%
<i>Paranthropus</i>	P ₃ (n = 14)	85.7%	7.1%	7.1%	21.4%	57.1%	21.4%
	P ₄ (n = 11)	90.9%	9.1%	0.0%	9.1%	63.6%	27.3%

H. antecessor (Martínez de Pinillos *et al.* 2017). However, in earlier hominins trigonid crest expression is variable and appears to be less taxonomically informative. MH1 has a continuous trigonid crest in the M₁, which is most common in *Australopithecus* (7/10), however it is also relatively common in *Paranthropus* (4/10), and present in one of the three *Homo* M₁s that could be scored for this feature. The lack of continuous trigonid crests in MH2 and the M₃ of MH1 is common in all taxa – particularly *Paranthropus* (no M₂ or M₃ showed a continuous trigonid crest), but this is also common in *Australopithecus* and *Homo*. Previous studies have found that trigonid crest presence decreases distally along the tooth row in *H. sapiens* (Bailey *et al.* 2011; Wu & Turner 1993), *Pan* (Bailey *et al.* 2011) and molars from Tighenif (Zanolli & Mazurier 2013), but not in Neanderthals where trigonid crests are extremely common in all molar positions, which appears to be a derived condition (Bailey *et al.* 2011). The interindividual data presented here suggest that *Australopithecus* and *Paranthropus* also show a decrease in continuous trigonid crest presence across the tooth row, while early *Homo* has the highest frequency in the M₂ (Table 4); although the small sample sizes here, particularly in the M₁, should warrant caution. In *A. sediba*, the more typical early hominin pattern is seen, with both individuals showing evidence of a reduction in trigonid crest expression across the tooth row. However, one difference between the two individuals is that while the M₃ of MH1 does not have a continuous trigonid crest, there are still well-developed essential ridges on both cusps that deflect mesially, similar to the pattern seen in Zhoukoudian M₂ PA70 (Xing *et al.* 2018; Bermúdez de Castro *et al.* 2021).

Among premolar traits, continuous mesial and distal marginal ridges, as seen in both *A. sediba* individuals (P₃ and P₄), are common in *Australopithecus*, *Paranthropus* and *Homo*, so are not taxonomically informative (Table 5). This is also true of the continuous transverse crests seen in the P₃s of MH1 and MH2, and the P₄ of MH1. The P₄ of MH2, while worn, shows no transverse crest in the occlusal basin – this is most common in *Paranthropus*, but is also found rarely in *Australopithecus* (1/13). The buccal groove pattern seen in the P₃ of MH1 (Type 1, 2) is not found within the *Homo* sample here (n = 6), but is seen in some *Australopithecus* and *Paranthropus* P₃s, while the marked mesial buccal grooves seen in the P₄s of both *A. sediba* individuals are not seen in *Paranthropus* (n = 11).

Examination of internal dental structures also reveal an unusual aspect of the *A. sediba* dentition; the apparent rotation of the EDJ relative to the enamel in occlusal view, in some molars. This is clearest in the M₂ of MH1, but can also be seen to lesser degrees in other teeth such as the M₃ of MH1, as well as in the M₂ of MH2 (although the higher degree of wear makes this less clear). The reason for this apparent rotation is not clear, but likely involves differences in the distribution of enamel and the degree to which is “overhangs” the EDJ in occlusal view, which impacts the position of the cusps and orientation of crest features, giving the impression of a misalignment of the enamel and dentine crowns. This phenomenon merits further investigation in a broad hominin sample through analysis of the shape of the enamel surface, EDJ and the 3D distribution of enamel across the crown.

CONCLUSIONS

Overall, the EDJ of *A. sediba* mandibular postcanine teeth clarifies the expression of several key dental features, and fails to find dental traits that resemble early *Homo*. Instead, these teeth most closely resemble *Australopithecus*, despite the small size of the teeth, and derived tooth size patterns across the tooth row (Irish *et al.* 2016). Future work should consider discrete traits in the maxillary teeth, the morphology of the roots, and geometric morphometric analysis of EDJ shape.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX 1. — Molar enamel thickness measurements for MH1.

Tooth	Enamel Area (mm ²)	Dentine Area (mm ²)	EDJ Length (mm)	Bi-cervical diameter (mm)	AET (mm)	RET
RM ₂	35.22	41.69	20.54	12.13	1.71	26.56
RM ₃	37.09	45.39	20.56	11.84	1.80	26.78

APPENDIX 2. — Molar discrete traits comparative sample. Scores for lingual and distal accessory cusps are taken from Davies *et al.* (2021), while trigonid crest scores were made for this study following the scoring system of Bailey *et al.* (2011). Abbreviations: **ent**, entoconid type; **Hld**, hypoconulid type; **Int**, interconulid type; **Med**, metaconid type.

Accession	Site	Taxon	Grouping	Tooth position	Side	Lingual accessory cusps			Distal accessory cusps			Trigonid crest
						Int	Med	Ent	Int	Ent	Hld	
A.L. 145-35	Hadar, Ethiopia	<i>A. afarensis</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM1	L	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
A.L. 266-1	Hadar, Ethiopia	<i>A. afarensis</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM1	L	0	0	0	1	0	0	–
A.L. 288-1	Hadar, Ethiopia	<i>A. afarensis</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM1	R	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
A.L. 330-5	Hadar, Ethiopia	<i>A. afarensis</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM1	R	0	0	0	0	0	0	–
A.L. 330-7	Hadar, Ethiopia	<i>A. afarensis</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM1	L	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
A.L. 333w-1a	Hadar, Ethiopia	<i>A. afarensis</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM1	L	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
A.L. 417-1a	Hadar, Ethiopia	<i>A. afarensis</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM1	L	0	0	0	1	0	0	2
Sts 9	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM1	R	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
StW 145	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM1	R	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
StW 291	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM1	R	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
StW 309A	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM1	R	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
StW 421A	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM1	R	0	0	0	1	0	0	2
StW 537	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM1	L	0	0	0	0	0	0	–
DNH 60B	Drimolen, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LM1	R	0	0	0	1	0	0	2
SK 104	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LM1	L	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SK 23	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LM1	L	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
SK 25	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LM1	L	0	0	0	1	0	0	2
SK 6	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LM1	L	0	0	0	1	0	0	2
SK 61	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LM1	R	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
SK 828	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LM1	L	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
SK 843	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LM1	L	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
KNM-ER 15930	Koobi Fora, Kenya	<i>P. boisei</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LM1	L	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
KNM-ER 6080	Koobi Fora, Kenya	<i>P. boisei</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LM1	R	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
KNM-ER 1502	Koobi Fora, Kenya	<i>H. habilis</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LM1	R	1	0	0	0	0	0	–
KNM-ER 1802	Koobi Fora, Kenya	<i>H. habilis</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LM1	R	0	1	0	0	0	0	–
OH 7	Olduvai Gorge, Tanzania	<i>H. habilis</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LM1	L	0	2	0	0	0	0	0
OH 13	Olduvai Gorge, Tanzania	<i>H. habilis</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LM1	R	0	1	0	0	0	0	2
OH 16	Olduvai Gorge, Tanzania	<i>H. habilis</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LM1	R	0	1	0	0	0	0	–
OMO 75-69-15	Omo, Ethiopia	<i>H. habilis</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LM1	L	0	1	0	0	0	0	–
KNM-ER 806C	Koobi Fora, Kenya	<i>H. erectus</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LM1	L	1	1	0	0	0	0	1
KNM-ER 992	Koobi Fora, Kenya	<i>H. erectus</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LM1	R	0	1	0	0	0	0	–
KNM-BK 67	Baringo, Kenya	<i>H. erectus</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LM1	R	NA	NA	NA	0	0	0	–
OH 22	Olduvai Gorge, Tanzania	<i>H. erectus</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LM1	R	0	0	0	0	0	0	–
A.L. 145-35	Hadar, Ethiopia	<i>A. afarensis</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM2	L	1	0	0	1	0	0	2
A.L. 188-1	Hadar, Ethiopia	<i>A. afarensis</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM2	R	0	0	0	1	0	0	2
A.L. 241-14	Hadar, Ethiopia	<i>A. afarensis</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM2	L	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
A.L. 266-1	Hadar, Ethiopia	<i>A. afarensis</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM2	R	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
A.L. 288-1	Hadar, Ethiopia	<i>A. afarensis</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM2	R	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
A.L. 330-5	Hadar, Ethiopia	<i>A. afarensis</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM2	R	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
A.L. 333w-1a	Hadar, Ethiopia	<i>A. afarensis</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM2	L	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
A.L. 417-1a	Hadar, Ethiopia	<i>A. afarensis</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM2	L	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
A.L. 440-1	Hadar, Ethiopia	<i>A. afarensis</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM2	R	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
A.L. 443-1	Hadar, Ethiopia	<i>A. afarensis</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM2	L	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
StW 213	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM2	L	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
StW 3	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM2	L	0	1	0	2	0	1	1
StW 308	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM2	R	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
StW 412A	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM2	R	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
StW 424	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM2	L	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
StW 491	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM2	L	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
StW 537	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM2	L	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
StW 560E	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM2	R	0	1	0	1	0	0	1

APPENDIX 2. — Continuation.

Accession	Site	Taxon	Grouping	Tooth		Lingual accessory cusps			Distal accessory cusps			Trigonid crest
				position	Side	Int	Med	Ent	Int	Ent	Hld	
DNH 60C	Drimolen, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LM2	R	0	0	0	2	0	0	1
SK 1	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LM2	L	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
SK 23	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LM2	L	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
SK 25	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LM2	R	0	0	0	3	0	0	1
SK 5	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LM2	L	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
SK 6	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LM2	R	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
SK 843	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LM2	L	0	0	0	1	0	1	0
KNM-ER 15930	Koobi Fora, Kenya	<i>P. boisei</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LM2	L	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
KNM-ER 25520	Koobi Fora, Kenya	<i>P. boisei</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LM2	R	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
KNM-ER 1483E	Koobi Fora, Kenya	<i>Homo</i> sp.	<i>Homo</i>	LM2	L	0	0	0	0	0	1	–
KNM-ER 1507	Koobi Fora, Kenya	<i>Homo</i> sp.	<i>Homo</i>	LM2	L	0	0	0	1	0	0	–
KNM-ER 1802	Koobi Fora, Kenya	<i>H. habilis</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LM2	R	0	0	0	1	0	0	2
OH 7	Olduvai Gorge, Tanzania	<i>H. habilis</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LM2	L	1	0	0	2	0	0	0
OH 16	Olduvai Gorge, Tanzania	<i>H. habilis</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LM2	R	0	1	0	0	0	0	–
OMO 7-69-19	Omo, Ethiopia	<i>H. habilis</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LM2	L	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
KNM-ER 1808G	Koobi Fora, Kenya	<i>H. erectus</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LM2	R	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
KNM-ER 806B	Koobi Fora, Kenya	<i>H. erectus</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LM2	L	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
KNM-ER 992	Koobi Fora, Kenya	<i>H. erectus</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LM2	R	0	0	0	1	0	0	–
OH 22	Olduvai Gorge, Tanzania	<i>H. erectus</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LM2	R	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
KNM-BK 67	Baringo, Kenya	<i>H. erectus</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LM2	L	0	0	0	0	0	0	–
A.L. 188-1	Hadar, Ethiopia	<i>A. afarensis</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM3	R	0	0	0	1	0	0	2
A.L. 266-1	Hadar, Ethiopia	<i>A. afarensis</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM3	R	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
A.L. 288-1	Hadar, Ethiopia	<i>A. afarensis</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM3	R	1	0	0	2	0	0	1
A.L. 330-5	Hadar, Ethiopia	<i>A. afarensis</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM3	R	1	0	0	1	0	0	1
StW 280	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM3	R	0	0	0	1	0	1	1
StW 491	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM3	L	0	0	0	2	0	0	0
StW 520	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM3	R	0	0	0	0	0	2	1
StW 529	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM3	L	0	1	0	1	0	0	2
StW 537	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM3	L	0	0	0	1	0	1	2
StW 560A	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM3	R	1	1	0	2	0	0	1
Sts 59	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM3	L	0	1	1	1	0	0	0
TM 1520	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LM3	L	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
DNH 75	Drimolen, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LM3	L	0	0	0	2	0	0	1
SK 6	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LM3	R	0	0	0	1	0	1	0
SK 22	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LM3	R	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
SK 23	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LM3	L	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
SK 75	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LM3	R	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
KNM-ER 15930	Koobi Fora, Kenya	<i>P. boisei</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LM3	L	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
KNM-ER 25520	Koobi Fora, Kenya	<i>P. boisei</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LM3	R	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
KNM-ER 1480A	Koobi Fora, Kenya	<i>Homo</i> sp.	<i>Homo</i>	LM3	R	0	1	0	2	0	0	1
OH 4	Olduvai Gorge, Tanzania	<i>H. habilis</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LM3	L	1	0	0	0	0	1	1
OH 13	Olduvai Gorge, Tanzania	<i>H. habilis</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LM3	L	1	0	0	1	1	0	0
OH 16	Olduvai Gorge, Tanzania	<i>H. habilis</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LM3	R	1	0	0	0	0	0	–
OH 27	Olduvai Gorge, Tanzania	<i>H. habilis</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LM3	R	1	0	0	1	0	1	2
OMO 75-69-16	Omo, Ethiopia	<i>H. habilis</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LM3	R	1	0	0	0	0	0	–
KNM-ER 1812C	Koobi Fora, Kenya	<i>H. erectus</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LM3	L	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
KNM-ER 806A	Koobi Fora, Kenya	<i>H. erectus</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LM3	L	0	0	0	0	1	1	1
KNM-ER 992	Koobi Fora, Kenya	<i>H. erectus</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LM3	L	0	0	0	0	0	0	–
KNM-BK 67	Baringo, Kenya	<i>H. erectus</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LM3	R	0	1	0	0	0	0	1

APPENDIX 3. — Premolar discrete traits comparative sample. Scoring system follows Davies *et al.* 2019. *, these specimens have crests on both the protoconid and metaconid that overlap in the occlusal basin, but do not meet, which is outside of the Davies *et al.* (2019) scoring system. **, the protoconid crest on SKX 21204 LP4 deflects mesially rather than distally as is typical for other type 2 crests. Abbreviations: **C**, continuous marginal ridges; **D**, distal marginal ridge discontinuous; **M**, mesial marginal ridge discontinuous; **MD**, mesial and distal marginal ridges discontinuous.

Accession	Site	Taxon	Grouping	Tooth position	Side	Scoring source	Transverse Crest	Marginal Ridge	Mesial buccal groove	Distal buccal groove
AL266-1	Hadar, Ethiopia	<i>A. afarensis</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LP3	R	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	1	M	1	1
AL333-10	Hadar, Ethiopia	<i>A. afarensis</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LP3	L	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	1	C	2	2
AL333w-1c	Hadar, Ethiopia	<i>A. afarensis</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LP3	R	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	1	M	2	2
AL655-1	Hadar, Ethiopia	<i>A. afarensis</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LP3	L	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	1	–	–	–
STW 7	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LP3	L	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	1	C	1	1
STW 104	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LP3	L	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	1	C	2	1
STW 142	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LP3	R	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	–	C	2	1
STW 193	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LP3	R	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	–	–	2	1
STW 213	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LP3	R	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	1	M	2	2
STW 401	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LP3	R	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	–	D	2	2
STW 404	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LP3	R	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	–	C	2	1
STW 420B	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LP3	L	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	1	C	2	2
STW 498c	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LP3	L	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	–	C	2	1
STS 24	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LP3	L	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	1	C	1	1
STS 51	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LP3	R	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	1	C	2	1
STS 52b	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LP3	R	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	–	C	2	2
Taung1	Taung, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LP3	R	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	1	M	2	1
DNH8	Drimolen, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LP3	L	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	1	C	0	1
DNH46	Drimolen, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LP3	R	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	1	–	–	–
DNH51	Drimolen, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LP3	R	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	–	C	0	1
DNH107	Drimolen, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LP3	L	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	1	C	0	2
SK23	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LP3	L	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	–	C	0	0
SK30	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LP3	L	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	–	–	0	1
SK61	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LP3	R	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	1	C	0	1
SK62	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LP3	L	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	1	C	1	2
SK63	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LP3	L	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	–	–	0	1
SK100	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LP3	R	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	1	C	0	1
SK857	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LP3	R	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	1	C	0	0
SKW5	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LP3	R	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	–	C	0	1
KNM-WT 16005	West Turkana, Kenya	<i>P. aethiopicus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LP3	L	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	1	C	0	1
KNM-ER 1820	Koobi Fora, Kenya	<i>P. boisei</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LP3	L	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	1	C	–	–
KNM-ER 6082	Koobi Fora, Kenya	<i>P. boisei</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LP3	L	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	0	C	–	–
KNM-ER 15951H	Koobi Fora, Kenya	<i>P. boisei</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LP3	L	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	–	–	0	0
L427-7	Omo, Ethiopia	<i>P. boisei</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LP3	R	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	0	–	2	2
OH 6	Olduvai Gorge, Tanzania	<i>H. habilis</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LP3	L	This study	1	C	2	1
OH 7	Olduvai Gorge, Tanzania	<i>H. habilis</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LP3	R	This study	1	C	0	0
OH 13	Olduvai Gorge, Tanzania	<i>H. habilis</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LP3	R	This study	1	C	–	–
OH 16	Olduvai Gorge, Tanzania	<i>H. habilis</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LP3	R	This study	1a	M	2	1
KNM-ER 806E	Koobi Fora, Kenya	<i>Homo</i> sp. (<i>H. ergaster</i>)	<i>Homo</i>	LP3	L	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	–	–	2	0

APPENDIX 3. — Continuation.

Accession	Site	Taxon	Grouping	Tooth		Scoring source	Transverse Crest	Marginal Ridge	Mesial buccal groove	Distal buccal groove
				position	Side					
SKX 21204	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>Homo</i> sp. (<i>H. ergaster</i>)	<i>Homo</i>	LP3	R	Davies <i>et al.</i> 2019	1	C	2	1
OH 22	Olduvai Gorge, Tanzania	<i>H. erectus</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LP3	R	This study	1	M	2	0
A.L. 266-1	Hadar, Ethiopia	<i>A. afarensis</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LP4	R	This study	1	C	0	1
A.L. 330-7	Hadar, Ethiopia	<i>A. afarensis</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LP4	L	This study	1	C	0	1
A.L. 330-5	Hadar, Ethiopia	<i>A. afarensis</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LP4	R	This study	1	–	0	1
A.L. 417-1a	Hadar, Ethiopia	<i>A. afarensis</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LP4	L	This study	1	C	0	1
A.L. 443-1	Hadar, Ethiopia	<i>A. afarensis</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LP4	L	This study	1	C	0	1
Sts 52b	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LP4	R	This study	*	C	2	2
StW 14	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LP4	L	This study	1	C	0	0
StW 131	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LP4	L	This study	1	C	2	2
StW 213	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LP4	R	This study	0	C	1	2
StW 327	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LP4	R	This study	1	C	1	1
StW 404	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LP4	R	This study	1	C	2	0
StW 537	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LP4	L	This study	1	C	2	1
TM 1523	Sterkfontein, South Africa	<i>A. africanus</i>	<i>Australopithecus</i>	LP4	L	This study	1	C	0	0
SK7	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LP4	R	This study	0	C	0	1
SK23	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LP4	R	This study	1	C	0	0
SK55B	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LP4	L	This study	1	C	0	1
SK88	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LP4	L	This study	1	C	0	1
SK826B	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LP4	L	This study	0	C	0	2
SK1587a	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LP4	L	This study	*	C	1	2
SK1588	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LP4	R	This study	1	C	0	1
SKW5	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>P. robustus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LP4	R	This study	1	C	0	2
KNM-WT 16005	West Turkana, Kenya	<i>P. aethiopicus</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LP4	L	This study	0	–	–	–
KNM-ER 3885	Koobi Fora, Kenya	<i>P. boisei</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LP4	R	This study	0	C	0	1
KNM-ER 15951D	Koobi Fora, Kenya	<i>P. boisei</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LP4	R	This study	0	C	0	1
L427-7	Omo, Ethiopia	<i>P. boisei</i>	<i>Paranthropus</i>	LP4	R	This study	1	C	0	1
OH 7	Olduvai Gorge, Tanzania	<i>H. habilis</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LP4	R	This study	1	C	0	0
OH 13	Olduvai Gorge, Tanzania	<i>H. habilis</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LP4	L	This study	1	C	1	1
OH 16	Olduvai Gorge, Tanzania	<i>H. habilis</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LP4	L	This study	1	C	1	2
SKX 21204	Swartkrans, South Africa	<i>H. erectus</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LP4	R	This study	2**	C	2	2
OH 22	Olduvai Gorge, Tanzania	<i>H. erectus</i>	<i>Homo</i>	LP4	R	This study	1	C	–	–